

EROSION TESTING OF FILLED AND/OR REINFORCED VINYL ESTER COMPOSITES IN WATER MEDIUM AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports slurry erosion testing of vinyl ester matrix composites. The effect of resin type, filler and glass fibre reinforcement was studied at elevated temperatures. Slurry erosion is commonly observed in almost all kinds of components and engineering parts that are in contact with flowing slurry. Conditions containing harsh chemicals at elevated temperature are demanding to the metallic materials so vinyl ester matrix composites, which can tolerate these conditions, are commonly used.

Erosion testing was done in pilot-scale reactor which mimics actual service environment as close as possible. Total of nine different material combinations were tested and dominating wear mechanism of the samples was found to be abrasive wear and cavitation. Due to the elevated testing temperature, heat distortion temperature of the resins had a significant role to the erosion resistance. Incorporating either filler or reinforcement improved the erosion resistance more effectively than adding both simultaneously to the composite structure. These complex material combinations needs to be further studied.

1 INTRODUCTION

Vinyl ester matrix composites have excellent chemical resistance and good mechanical properties. These properties are the reason why vinyl ester composites are commonly used in harsh chemical environments of hydrometallurgical process industry, pulp and paper industry and waste water treatment plants [1]. Vinyl ester composites are used in various components and engineering parts where these materials may be subjected to slurry erosion wear, the elevated temperature as high as 100 °C and various chemical environments [2].

1.1 Slurry erosion

The slurry erosion is a phenomenon which causes severe damage to the materials. Slurry can be described as a mixture of solid particles in a liquid (usually water) of such consistency that it can be readily pumped. Slurry erosion is defined as the type of wear that is experienced by a material exposed to a high-velocity stream of slurry. Material is removed from a target surface by the action of solid particles in the liquid medium. The erosion occurs either when the material moves at a certain velocity through the slurry or when the slurry moves past the material at a certain velocity. The wear response of a given material in certain slurry does not indicate how that material would respond to the different kind of slurry. Similarly, the effect of certain slurry on one material does not indicate how it would affect another material. Also the influence of slurry concentration should be recognized [3]. Although

the wear effect of slurry erosion has been known for a long time, still understanding of this phenomenon is quite poor because of its complexity [4,5].

There are various parameters that affect slurry erosion of the composite materials: the tribological parameters related to abrasive particle properties (type, shape, size, density, hardness, physical and chemical properties), equipment properties (temperature, impact velocity, impact angle and time) and material properties (matrix properties, reinforcement properties and adhesion between them). It has been noted that the material removal during erosion depends on many interrelated factors, number can exceed 20, among which velocity and the impact angle are the most influential [6-8].

Polymers and their composites have higher erosion rates than metals, due to polymers semi-ductile erosion behaviour. It is also well known that erosion rate of polymer composites is usually higher when comparing to the neat polymers [L10, L11]. When composite materials are exposed to slurry erosion wear the erosion rate is strongly influenced by matrix material whether it is thermoset or thermoplastic. Also the reinforcing fibre brittleness and strength of the interfacial bonding between the matrix materials and the reinforcing fibres are important. Although, neat polymers do not have as good mechanical properties as polymer composites. Using composites is still justified due to their strength, light weight and chemical resistance. The erosion wear of composite materials is reported to follow these three steps:

1. Local removal of material in resin rich zones
2. Erosion in fiber zone associated with fibre breakage and
3. Erosion of the interface between fibers and matrix material.

By altering the matrix properties, the erosion resistance can be enhanced because erosion starts at the matrix. If erosion resistance of the matrix can be raised it can protect brittle fibres longer from erosion [8], because brittle fibres in the polymer matrix (thermoset, thermoplastic) leads to compositions with lower erosion resistance [10-12].

Several research groups have conducted studies concerning the erosion of glass fibre reinforced composites and the erosion wear of composite samples containing different kinds of fillers, for example, Al_2O_3 , SiC, basalt and fly ash [8,9,11,13-15]. The function of filler in composite structure is considered more as a modifier than a true reinforcing agent due to low the percentage of the filler [8]. Incorporation of hard ceramic particles as filler is reported to increase the bulk hardness of composites but wear also depends upon the hardness of erodent particles [6]. Subsequently, filler forms a barrier that prevents the penetration of abrasive material to the sample resulting decrease in erosion wear. The filler also absorbs kinetic energy of the erodent during the test. This lowers the amount of energy absorbed to the matrix material and also to reinforcing fibre material. Improvement in the erosion wear resistance depends on the filler type and its concentration in composite structure [8,14,16].

A. Patnaik *et al.* [8] has reported that by incorporating both reinforcing fiber and filler to polymer composite structure it is possible to achieve a combination that improves properties and wear resistance. This combination can improve composite structure's modulus, impact toughness and reduce material costs. The erosion resistance of polyester glass fibre composites is also reported to improve with the incorporation of Al_2O_3 filler [13].

The effect of the testing parameters has been widely investigated but only a couple of studies have been performed at elevated temperatures. The testing temperature is an important factor since material properties change significantly as a function of temperature. The mechanical behaviour can affect the mechanisms of mass removal from the surface. In polymeric materials differences in the erosion resistance as a function of temperature can be expected when behaviour changes from rigid to rubbery.

The aim of this research was to study the influence of the vinyl ester matrix type, silicon dioxide (SiO_2) filler and glass fibre reinforcement on slurry erosion behaviour at elevated temperature when testing parameters was kept constant. Effect of the test parameters on vinyl matrix composites in high temperature slurry erosion has been reported in a previous article [18].

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Slurry erosion test reactor

The in-house slurry erosion test reactor used in this study mimics the actual service environment of the reactors used in the hydrometallurgical industry. Test apparatus (Figure 1) was constructed of a shaft, which joined a motor to an agitator. The motor rotates and the shaft transfers movement to the agitator.

The six blades of the agitator, fixed at 45° position, can hold 12 samples at a time. Samples were attached to the agitator by frames, revealing 32 mm x 32 mm area of the sample surface. This area was exposed to the erosive slurry environment whereas the edges of the samples were protected by the frames. The pressure side of each blade experienced a uniform pressure whereas the suction side felt more turbulent flow, due to clockwise rotating movement.

Figure 1: Slurry erosion test reactor and the agitator blades holding the samples. Modified from [18]

2.2 Sample materials and preparation

In this study nine different material combinations were examined. Materials were manufactured as a laminate and then cut either by water jet cutter or band saw. Final sample size was 35 mm x 35 mm and the target thickness 3 mm.

Pure vinyl ester resin samples (Derakane 411-350, Derakane 441-400, Derakane 470-300 supplied by Ashland) and resins including SiO₂ filler (411+SiO₂, 441+SiO₂, 470+SiO₂) were manufactured in an open mould. The filler used was Silbond 600 VST SiO₂ (supplied by HPF the Mineral Engineers) treated with vinylsilane and with average grain size of 4 μm. Resins were mixed with MEKP initiator and Co-nap6% accelerator. For filled samples, 20 w-% of SiO₂ filler was mixed to the matrix carefully before the accelerator. After final blending and removing bubbles with vacuum treatment, samples were cured for 24 h at room temperature (RT) and then post-cured for 6 h at 80 °C.

Samples containing fiber reinforcements (411+GF, 441+GF) were manufactured by hand-lay up. Fibers used were C-glass and E-glass fiber chopped strand mats with the nominal weight of 30 g/m² and 300 g/m². Laminates included six layers of 300 g/m² mat and one layer of the surface veil (30 g/m²) on both surfaces. Curing of the samples was similar to pure resin samples.

The last set of samples were hybrids of SiO₂ filler and glass fiber reinforcement in Derakane 441-350 resin (441+GF+SiO₂). Laminated samples included one C-glass 30 g/m² surface veil on both surfaces and four layers of chopped E-glass strand mat 300 g/m². Total glass fiber content in laminates was 25-30 %. The filler was the same Silbond 600 VST and approximately 15 w-% was added. After the curing, the samples were water jet cut to the testing size.

Before exposing samples to the erosive environment all samples were dried for 6 h at 80 °C and weighted. This was done to establish a fixed reference state. After 72 h erosion test samples were washed in water in order to remove the attached erodent particles and ultrasonically cleaned. Similar drying and weighting were executed as before testing.

Sample	Resin	Filler	Reinforcement
Derakane 411	411-350	-	-
Derakane 441	441-400	-	-
Derakane 470	470-300	-	-
411 + SiO ₂	411-350	SiO ₂ , 600 VST	-
441 + SiO ₂	441-400	SiO ₂ , 600 VST	-
470 + SiO ₂	470-300	SiO ₂ , 600 VST	-
411 + GF	411-350	-	C- and E- glass
441 + GF	441-400	-	C- and E- glass
441+ GF + SiO ₂	441-400	SiO ₂ , 600 VST	C- and E- glass

Table 1: Tested samples.

2.3 Testing conditions

The rotation speed used in the tests was 600 rpm meaning 4.8 m/s velocity at the tip of the blade. It is known that during testing that different pressure distribution is generated to the pressure and suction sides of agitator blades. Flow is more uniform on the pressure side of the blade although the velocity varies slightly (3.5 %) across the sample surface due to the different local velocities of the blade. On the suction side of the blade, the trailing vortex is generated leading to more localized wear [18].

The reactor was filled with tap water and fine quartz sand (0.05-0.2 mm), supplied by Sibelco Nordic Oy Ab, (Figure 2) with concentration of 15 w-% up to 180 litres. The sand particles were irregular in shape with sharp edges which are responsible for erosion [4]. Fresh slurry sand was used in every test because the erosion rate in recycled slurry is smaller than in fresh slurry due to the tendency of the particles to get rounded on impacts [19]. In addition heating coils were used to heat up the slurry to a test temperature 95 °C and temperature was monitored continuously with thermocouples. Duration of each test was 72 h.

Figure 2: Scanning electron microscopy image of Fine quartz sand

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results for the erosion mass losses of the vinyl ester matrix composites with glass fibre reinforcement and SiO₂ under test conditions with constant impact angle, slurry concentration, water medium, abrasive material, temperature, test duration and rotation speed are presented in following sub-chapters. In addition, the differences between the pressure and suction side samples are analysed.

3.1 Pressure side

Figure 3 presents erosion weight losses and Barcol hardness measurement results of the pressure side samples. Erosion mass losses are given by the columns and the lines present the Barcol hardness results.

Figure 3: The erosion wear columns and Barcol hardness results (line and markers) of the pressure side samples

Effect of resin type can be seen in figure 3 at upper left side. Derakane 411-350 has a heat distortion temperature (HDT) 105 °C that is 15 °C lower than the HDT of Derakane 441-400 and 45°C lower than the HDT of Derakane 470-300 resin [20-22]. In addition, hardness of samples showed a similar ranking: 411 had lowest hardness and 470 the highest. Slurry erosion wear mass losses of Derakane 411 and Derakane 441 samples were relatively the same but Derakane 470 samples showed double slurry erosion. Due to the high HDT of Derakane 470 it is brittle at test temperature, which might affect to the erosion resistance of the resin. Because Derakane 411 and 441 resins were softer, they would absorb kinetic energy of the erodent particles more easily. Thus, the mass loss was smaller in these samples.

Effect of filler to the erosion is presented at upper right side of figure 3. The incorporation of the filler led to increase in the hardness of composites. The addition of the fillers lowered the mass losses

of the softer resins 411 and 441. In contrast, for the harder 470 resin an opposite behavior was detected i.e. the erosion mass loss increased from 0.5 wt-% to 0.8 wt-%. For the softer resins 411 and 441 the increased hardness caused by the fillers probably acted as a barrier for penetration of the abrasive particles therefore limiting the material damage which was seen as lower mass loss. On the other hand in the harder 470 the addition of the fillers could have increased the brittleness leading to higher mass losses.

Effect of glass fiber reinforcement is shown in lower left side of figure 3. In the tested Derakane 441 samples glass fibers were mostly intact and the surface quality was smooth. The tested Derakane 411 resin was evenly eroded from sample surface which led to the revealing of the brittle glass fibers. Despite of the similar erosion behavior of 411 and 441 resins the addition of glass fibers to 441 resin did not similarly increase the erosion mass loss as it did with 411 resin. Surface quality of the tested samples can be seen in figure 4.

Combining both reinforcements and filler to Derakane 441 vinyl ester resin increased the mass loss when compared to glass fiber reinforced samples. Weight loss was 20 times higher than in the samples with only SiO₂ filler. This indicated a potential interaction between the fillers and the reinforcement. To identify the exact nature of this interaction further characterization is required. Large mass loss can result from high density of the used filler particles. Surface quality was approximately the same as in the glass fiber reinforced samples as illustrated in figure 4.

Figure 4: Derakane 411+ GF, Derakane 441 + GF and Derakane 441+ GF + SiO₂ pressure side samples after erosion testing.

3.2 Suction side

Figure 5 presents erosion weight losses and Barcol hardness measurement results of the suction side samples.

Figure 5: The erosion wear columns and Barcol hardness results (line and markers) of the suction side samples

Slurry flow around the blades causes a trailing vortex and cavitation to the suction side sample surface. The trailing vortex was created to the inner side, close to the shaft axis. At the testing temperature 95°C also gas bubbles started to format, which was additional factor to the local environment causing erosion of the sample [18]. Particle-gas interactions might lower the kinetic energy of the erodent particles and also influence the properties of the trailing vortex. All this led to higher mass loss in the suction side samples. Effect of the resin type in suction side is shown in upper left side. The hardness of the Derakane 441 and 470 seemed to have positive effect on the local erosion resistance which was opposite to the behavior of the pressure side samples. For Derakane 411 the test temperature was so close to the HDT of 105°C, that ductile samples did not resist extensive local erosion caused by the trailing vortex.

As shown in figure 5 in the upper right side, the addition of the filler to the Derakane 411 increased its erosion resistance. Hard particles can form barrier which prevents the penetration of erodent material. Due to the softness of the matrix and hardness of the filler, this material combination tolerated the local erosion better when compared to the other tested resins filler combinations. In case of 441 and 470 resins that as neat resin showed better erosion resistance the addition of the fillers increased the mass losses. In figure 6 localize erosion wear of the tested samples can be seen.

Figure 6: Derakane 411 + SiO₂, Derakane 441 + SiO₂ and Derakane 470 + SiO₂ suction side samples after erosion testing.

Glass fiber reinforcements had a positive effect to the erosion resistance on both studied 411 and 441 resins. The neat 441 tolerated erosion better than 411. Same trend was seen on reinforced samples but not in the filled samples. When testing samples containing both filler and reinforcement fibers, mass loss increased. Reason behind this was the high density of the filler particles. Sample contains high quantity of reinforcement fibers and fillers so the adhesion between matrix and other materials was essential.

Figure 7: Derakane 411 + GF, Derakane 441 + GF and Derakane 441 + GF + SiO₂ suction side samples after erosion testing.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, vinyl ester composites erosion resistance at elevated temperature was investigated in a pilot-scale reactor. The effect of resin type, filler and glass fibre reinforcement were studied, in total nine different material combinations were investigated. Difference between suction and pressure side behaviour was also analysed.

The low HDT of the Derakane 411 which transferred to a more ductile matrix seemed to have a positive effect when abrasive erosion on pressure side occurred. Although on suction side ductile behaviour was prone to cavitation caused by the trailing vortex. Resin erosion resistance against abrasive and cavitation erosion can be improved by addition of SiO₂ filler.

Erosion rate of Derakane 441 can be decreased by incorporating filler or glass fibre reinforcement to the matrix when sample is tested on the pressure side. Derakane 441 resin with glass fiber reinforcement withstood the local cavitation on suction side better than other combinations of this resin.

On suction side the abrasive particles did not penetrate to the hard surface of Derakane 470. Although due to abrasive erosion on pressure side the brittleness had negative effect. The addition of the filler, which increased hardness, and thus the brittleness even more, led to high erosion wear.

Tested material set was problematic due to different densities of matrix, reinforcement and filler. Relatively small amount of removed SiO₂ filler causes large mass loss due to its high density. The wear volume of the materials will be measured later on. The erosion test with all the different parameters caused unexpected erosion mass losses. Especially material combinations containing both filler and reinforcement, needs to be studied further.

It is recommended that erosion testing of samples is carried out in conditions that mimics actual service environment as close as possible. A further study is needed in view of scientific understanding and commercial importance.

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